

Radical-induced Chain Reactions in Solution. Part I. A Kinetic Study of the Oxidation of Oxalate by Iodine, Induced by Cobalt (III)

E. M. Kurian and S. Ghosh

Kinetics of the reaction of iodine with oxalic acid, induced by tripositive cobalt, has been investigated over a wide range of conditions and the rate law describing the data has been developed. The reaction is of first order with respect to both iodine and the reductant and the rate varies directly with the Co(III) concentration. The data are interpreted by a chain mechanism involving atomic iodine and oxalate free radical formed from bivalent oxalate anion by the action of OH, generated by the action of Co(III) on water. As the ratio of the concentration of iodine to that of the anion oxalate decreases, the chain-breaking step changes from an association of atomic iodine to a reaction of this substance with the oxalate free radical. The slow step in the reaction is the production of $C_2O_4^{1-}$ by the action of atomic iodine on oxalate anion. The overall activation energy of the reaction is found to be 26800 cal. and hence an activation energy of 8000 cal. may be attributed to the reaction of oxalate free radical with iodine.

In the present study, observations on the reaction:

induced by cobalt (III) are reported. Analysis of the rate data collected during the study has led to conclusions about the mechanism of this induced chain reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were either of AnalaR or E. Merck's G. R. specifications or of equivalent standard. All solutions were brought to the thermostat temperature and then mixed in the reaction vessel, coated with black Japan, also previously thermostated. Aliquots were withdrawn at definite intervals of time, the reaction was quenched by addition of aliquots in excess of potassium iodide, and the iodine was titrated against standard hypo, using starch as indicator. As the loss of iodine by evaporation was found negligible at the temperature and conditions of the reactions, no correction for it was felt necessary. The concentrations of iodine in reaction systems at different time intervals were estimated from the titre values.

Oxalate-oxalic acid mixtures of various pHs were obtained by adding the requisite quantity of potassium bicarbonate to a standard oxalic acid solution so that the concentration of the total reductant, viz., oxalic acid and oxalate, was kept the same. In the preparation of the oxalic-oxalate buffer, the amount of bicarbonate present in the potassium carbonate complex was also taken into account. pH values of reaction mixtures were measured with a Radio pH-meter of reproducibility ± 0.001 . The concentration of oxalate was assumed to be equivalent to the concentration of potassium bicarbonate added to oxalic acid.

Cobalt(III) in the form of potassium cobaltic carbonate was prepared by the method of Laitinen and Burdett¹.

Since the reaction between iodine and oxalic acid took place in dark even in absence of inductors, some experiments on the rate of the uninduced reaction were performed under identical conditions. Specific rate of this reaction was found to be of the order of 3.4×10^{-5} moles litre⁻¹ sec⁻¹ (at pH 5.27; temp. 30°; $[I_2] = 5 \times 10^{-4} M$; $[oxalate] = 9.8 \times 10^{-2} M$; $[oxalic\ acid] = 0.2 \times 10^{-2} M$), which is significantly low as compared to the specific rate 10.63×10^{-4} moles litre⁻¹ sec⁻¹ under identical conditions in presence of tripositive cobalt, as low as $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$, indicating induced oxidation of oxalate by iodine with cobalt (III).

At higher $[I_2]/[C_2O_4^{2-}]$ ratio, there was an initial rapid reduction of iodine, corresponding to the concentration of the cobalt (III), but little or no induced chain oxidation followed it. Consequently, the induction factor gradually decreased to the limiting value of one.

At lower $[I_2]/[C_2O_4^{2-}]$ ratio (i.e., the mixture of pH > 3.38), in all the cases the first order rate constants were found so high in the first few minutes that some iodine was immediately consumed on addition of cobalt(III) to the reaction mixture. This was followed by a regular consumption of iodine, obeying the first order kinetics. The values at different pHs and temperatures are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

$$[I_2] = 5 \times 10^{-4} M. [Co(III)] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} M.$$

[Oxalic acid].	[Oxalate].	pH.	$k \times 10^4$ moles litre ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ at		
			20°.	25°.	30°.
$4.0 \times 10^{-2} M$	$6.0 \times 10^{-2} M$	3.38	1.468	3.332	7.610
2.0	8.0	4.10	1.606	4.042	8.664
1.0	9.0	4.48	1.864	4.316	9.912
0.2	9.8	5.27	2.082	4.501	10.630

The data at other concentrations of Co(III) and those of the reductant were found to be of similar trend, and hence excluded.

The concentration of the total reductant, which was in large excess, was also varied, but the pH, concentration of the inductor and also the temperature were kept the same. It is clear from the results recorded in Table II that the values of the quotients (first order constants, k , divided by the respective reductant concentrations) are fairly constant.

TABLE II

Constancy of quotient $k/[reductant]$ at 25° and pH 4.10.

[Reductant] $\times 10^2 M$..	5.0	10.0	20.0
$k \times 10^4$..	2.142	4.316	8.546
$k/[reductant] \times 10^3$..	4.28	4.32	4.27

The results at other *pH*s and temperatures and cobaltic concentrations, within limits, led to the similar fact noted in Table II. Thus the reaction is also of first order with respect to the reductant so that the total order of reaction is found to be 2 when the reaction has become regular.

The impact of cobalt(III) concentration on the reaction rate between oxalate and iodine is shown in Table III.

TABLE III

[Oxalic acid] = $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$. [Oxalate] = $9.0 \times 10^{-2} M$. *pH* = 4.48.
[I₂] = $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. Temp. = 25°.

[Co(III)].	$k \times 10^4$ moles litre ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ .	$k/[Co(III)]$.
$2.50 \times 10^{-5} M$	4.30	17.2
5.00	8.60	17.2
7.50	13.00	17.3
10.00	17.40	17.4

The rate constant is therefore directly proportional to the concentration of Co(III); a plot of *k* as ordinate against [Co(III)] as abscissa provides a straight line passing through the origin (figure omitted).

Very low concentrations of iodide ions, used in the form of potassium iodide before the addition of [Co(III)], repressed the induced reaction due to the operation of

as iodide ion formed *in situ* was not found to be effective, whereas it should have been effective had the depression been due to

The addition of manganese(II) was found to effectively retard the oxidation remarkably, induced by Co(III), but showed quantitatively the same effect as if an equivalent amount of manganese(III) had been put in. The results therefore show that the net effect on the reaction is the production of manganese(III), equivalent to cobalt(III) concentration, and the mechanism of induction, now initiated, is probably due to the breaking of man- ganic oxalate complex, suggested for the induction observed for the oxidation of oxalate by the halogens^{2,3}.

The effect of *pH* or the ratio $[\text{I}_2]/[\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}]$ on the reaction rate, as reported here, has been discussed (*vide infra*).

The temperature coefficient for the reaction between 20° and 30° is calculated to be 4.6 from the results recorded in Table I. The values of the energy of activation, entropy of activation, and frequency factor are found to be 26800 cal., 29.46 e.u., and 2.5×10^{19} litres mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹ respectively. Incidentally, for the dark reaction between oxalate and iodine, the temperature coefficient⁴ is as high as about 7.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 1418.

3. *Ibid.*, 1948, **70**, 3928.

4. *Dhar, J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917 **111**, 748.

DISCUSSION

The induced oxidation of oxalate by iodine with cobalt (III), in the form of potassium cobaltic carbonate, proceeding *via* a chain mechanism for the chain length $[I_2]/[Co^{III}]$ at favourable conditions is as high as forty. The chain reaction is initiated by the action of cobalt (III) on water and not by the formation of a complex with oxalate; its disproportionation as the anion $Co(C_2O_4)_2^-$ is stable in an excess of oxalate. It was substantiated by the absence of any induced reaction on the addition of potassium cobaltic oxalate to the reaction mixture of the reductant and iodine. The formation of cobaltic oxalate complex and the generation of $C_2O_4^{1-}$ by its disproportionation are therefore improbable and hence the mechanism suggested by Taube²⁻³ for the induced reactivity of oxalate towards bromine and chlorine in presence of trivalent manganese and that by Ghosh and Kalra⁵ for the manganese(III)-induced oxidation of oxalate by iodine do not appear to hold good here, where cobalt(III) has been used as the inductor. An organic free radical is, however, formed in the oxidation of oxalate by cobalt (III), as a transient intermediate is shown by the fact that it is capable of reducing mercuric chloride and initiating polymerisation. Launer⁶ suggested the formation of Co_2^{1-} during the disproportionation of manganic oxalate. The existence of free radical $C_2O_4^{1-}$ has been postulated in the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine, both in dark and light⁷⁻⁹. In the mechanism⁹⁻¹¹, proposed by us, $C_2O_4^{1-}$ has been postulated to be the organic free radical though the general conclusions drawn will equally hold good even if we assume Co_2^{1-} or Co^{1+} as the reducing intermediates.

In the kinetics of the reduction of cobaltic salts by water, the existence of free hydroxyl radical as an intermediate has been revealed by Noyes and Deahl¹². We therefore assume that $C_2O_4^{1-}$ is generated through two consecutive reactions:

It is of interest here to compare this with the suggestion of Chakravarti and Ghosh¹³ of the formation of OH free radical by the interaction of Mn(III) and water. The OH radicals can initiate the chain and this has been further substantiated by our observation that the reaction:

induces the reduction of iodine by oxalate under comparable conditions.

We suggest that the following reactions immediately follow reaction (1):

5. Doctoral Thesis, Allahabad University, 1962.

6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 2597.

7. Abel, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, **154A**, 167.

8. Abel and Hilfording, *ibid.*, 1935, **172A**, 353.

9. Abel, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1937, **43**, 629.

10. Malaprade and Coulombesau, *Compt. rend.*, 1954, 2332.

11. Weiss, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, **2**, 188.

12. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **59**, 1337.

13. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1957, **207**, 392.

This cycle may be terminated:

It will be now interesting to compare this mechanism with those of Taube^{2,3} and of Ghosh and Kalra⁵.

In agreement with the experimental results, the sum of the reactions involved in the chain, excluding initiation and termination reactions, provides the stoichiometric relationship of equation (A).

The chain-termination reactions yield additional evidence in support of the mechanism advanced here, as will be shown from our subsequent considerations. When the chains are long, we may write $v_2 = v_3$ or

$$f_2 Z_2 [\text{I}_2] [\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}]_{\text{exp.}} (-8000/RT) = f_3 Z_3 [\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}] [\text{I}]_{\text{exp.}} (-18000/RT).$$

Hence

$$\frac{[\text{I}]}{[\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}]} = \frac{f_2 Z_2}{f_3 Z_3} \frac{[\text{I}_2]}{[\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}]} \exp. (10000/RT) \quad \dots \quad (a_1)$$

The expressions for steady state concentrations of $[\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}]$ and $[\text{I}]$, as obtained by the usual methods, also lead to a similar conclusion:

$$\frac{[\text{I}]}{[\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}]} = \frac{k_2 [\text{I}_2]}{k_3 [\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}]} \frac{v_3}{v_2} \quad \dots \quad (a_2)$$

where v_1, v_2, v_3 , etc. are the respective velocities of the reactions 1,2,3, etc.

$$v_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{v_1}{2} + \left(\frac{v_1^2}{4} + 2k_6 v_1 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad \dots \quad (b)$$

and

$$v_3 = 2k_6 v_1 \quad \dots \quad (c)$$

where

$$k_6 = \frac{k_2 k_3}{k_4} [\text{I}_2] [\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad (d)$$

and

$$v_1 = k_1 [\text{Co}^{3+}] / [\text{H}^+] \quad \dots \quad (e)$$

It is evident from equation (a₁) and (a₂) that as the ratio $[\text{I}_2]/[\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}]$ increases, the stationary concentration of atomic iodine will increase relative to that of $[\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}]$. On the basis of such considerations^{14,15}, we would expect the chain breaking by the association of two atomic iodines (step 5) to become important. As the ratio $[\text{I}_2]/[\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}]$ increases to a sufficiently high value, step (5) will dominate and compete with step (3), which generates the radical $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}$ after reaction (2) consuming the $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}$ obtained in step (1). Apart from this effect, the retarding effect on step (3) due to the increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ ion concentration too will add to the accumulation of atomic iodine in the system and the consequent loss of this active species by reaction (5). Thus when pH is low and

14. Taube and Bray, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 3372.

15. Taube, *ibid.*, 1942, **64**, 2473.

hence the ratio $[I_2]/[C_2O_4^{2-}]$ is high and v_3 low, reaction (5) is to be expected to dominate so that hardly may any chain be expected to propagate. This explains the low induction factor observed at low pH. It follows that at lower $[I_2]/[C_2O_4^{2-}]$ ratio, the important chain-termination reaction is (4) and is substantiated by the more or less the same induction factor observed in the pH range 3.38 to 5.37.

The reaction:

may also be advanced, but it is not of any importance as a ten-fold increase in cobalt (II) concentration is found to be of no effect on the induced reaction.

The initial rapid reduction of iodine is mainly due to the fast reactions (1) and (2). A reaction scheme consisting of the reactions (1), (2), (3), and (4), in which reaction (3) is assumed to be the rate-determining reaction and (4), the important chain-termination reaction at low $[I_2]/[C_2O_4^{2-}]$ ratio, leads to the rate equation:

$$\frac{-d[I_2]}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{v_1^2}{4} + 2k_6 v_2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{v_1}{2} \right] \quad \dots \quad (f)$$

From (f) it follows that the reduction of iodine is a function of v_1 , which has a high velocity, and that so long as v_1 is involved in the reaction, the reduction of iodine should naturally be very fast.

The kinetics of the reduction of iodine by oxalate in presence of cobalt(III), recorded herein, relates to the regular reaction that follows after the rapid initial consumption of iodine, when the chain breaking steps (4) and (5) are not significant to any appreciable extent. It is therefore obvious that for the portion of the reaction, of which the rate constants have been recorded, step (3) is the rate-determining one when step (2) is a fast one, as is to be understood from the initial rapid loss of iodine. This leads to the rate relation:

$$\frac{-d[I_2]}{dt} = k_3 k_2 k_1 [Co^{III}] [I_2] [C_2O_4^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad (g)$$

where it has been assumed that

and hence

$$[I] = k_2 k_1 [Co^{III}] [I_2]$$

This is in harmony with the experimental findings.

Griffith *et al.*¹⁶ have attributed an activation energy of 18000 cal. for the reaction of atomic iodine with oxalate ionic step (3). The activation energy for reaction (4) is expected to be small. We find the activation energy for the overall reaction to be about 26800 cal. Hence an activation energy of about 8000 cal. may be attributed to the reaction of $C_2O_4^{1-}$ with iodine, noted in step (2). This is comparable to the activation energies, which are usually less than 10000 cal. and more frequently between 3000 and 6000 cal. for free radical reactions and decompositions.

RADICAL-INDUCED CHAIN REACTIONS IN SOLUTION

The impact of cobalt (III) in the form of potassium cobaltic carbonate on the dark reaction between iodine and some hydroxy-acids, such as tartaric, citric, lactic, and mandelic, was also investigated and it was invariably observed that there was a rapid initial reduction of iodine, but little chain oxidation of the organic substrate followed it. This is to be expected if the production of organic free radical by the action of atomic iodine (cf. step 3) on the organic anion is too slow and the subsequent chain-breaking steps (4) and (5) become important because of the accumulation of atomic iodine in the system. It therefore remains to be seen if step (3) can be accelerated in presence of light and that the chain will proceed satisfactorily.

Thanks are due to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi; for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of the authors. (E.M.K.).

DEPARTMENT OF POST-GRADUATE STUDIES
AND RESEARCH IN CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF JABALPUR,
JABALPUR, M.P.

Received October 6, 1964.